

This is a pre-peer review version submitted for:

Melichar, G.; Schmidt-Boddy, P.; Fuchs, T. & Tewes, C. (eds.): *Phenomenology of Emotion: Perspectives from Philosophy, Psychopathology and Psychotherapy*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

Any feedback and comments welcome!

Vulnerability and Emotional Abilities: The Case of Narcissism

Philipp Schmidt-Boddy

Abstract

This chapter explores the intricate relationship between our emotional abilities—that is, our individual skills and capabilities to feel, engage in, sustain, or modify emotions—and the experience of vulnerability. It sheds light on three connections between our emotional life and how vulnerability manifests in our experience of self, world, and others. First, it introduces the notion of ‘affective mercy’ referring to the fact that we remain dependent on something that is not in our hands when we shape our own affective experiences. Second, proposing a view on emotions as modal experiences of value, it suggests that emotional experience always involves a sense of vulnerability. Third, from this rather *implicit* sense of vulnerability, *explicit* feelings of vulnerability are distinguished. To clarify the relevance of emotional abilities for the experience of vulnerability, the interplay of these three connections will be exemplified in the case of vulnerable narcissism.

Keywords: vulnerability, emotions, emotional abilities, phenomenology, vulnerable narcissism

Introduction

It's far from being a secret: our human life means to be fundamentally exposed to many things—events and processes—that we do not control or have any power over whatsoever. We inhabit a world that, in many regards, is placed right in front of us, as it were. As the phenomenologists say, it is *given* to us. Even in our most active engagement *with* the world, in our enactment of our lives through which we constitute meaning together with others, we need to accept how the world and others resonate with our doings. Interaction involves, inevitably, reception. Enactivism has gotten right that the things of the world that we experience cannot and are not simply read off from our perception but involve a history of our own activity and agency that lets us move around in the world before it is fully constituted for the eye. And yet, Husserl's famous *I can*, the deep-seated sense of our own motility and the correlating bodily sensations that precedes our perception of concrete objects remains bound to there being something that is given together with our bodily movement (Husserl 1973). No matter how pervasive the contribution of our own activity to our experience of the world may be, the latter remains shot through with a plethora of experiences of facticity. We are born into a certain society, at a certain point in time of humanity, in a particular family, and with a certain bodily constitution, to name just a few examples that no one will cast into doubt. Our most fundamental attitude towards the world is characterized by responsiveness, a structure of response. (Waldenfels 1994). It's true though that it is 'up to us'—a Stoic *eph' hēmin*—to make sense of whatever is put in front of us as we move around in the world.

Yet, and that is of crucial importance: no matter how we may choose ourselves to be, if choice is possible, no matter how we make sense of the world, our relationships to others, and our place within these contexts, facticity in its many faces will always be among those things that give meaning to our actions. We address the unpredictable, navigate the uncontrollable, compensate for the irreversible, or despair over the impossible. No human life is ever free of the exposition to something *external*. Names and concepts for the latter abound. But regardless of how we may understand it, it makes our lives irrevocably vulnerable. The exposition to our own unknowable ground is an *ontological* vulnerability. It defines our being and our relationship to being in general, however the latter is

called and conceived: being, reality, nature, cosmos, substance, infinity or alterity. Ontological vulnerability is the original ground for all our *experiences* of vulnerability. But that doesn't mean that we always experience or think about our vulnerability in this most basic or deepest sense as finite beings.

This reveals a complicated interrelation between vulnerability and our sense of different forms vulnerabilities. In this article, I do not want to and cannot elucidate the plethora of the entanglements between the two in their entirety. My aim is more modest, as I only wish to explore some connections between the two. I distinguish three of these, without claiming that my analysis is exhaustive. The first connection I look at concerns the vulnerability of emotional life in the sense that when we engage emotionally, we are exposed to and dependent on what I will call *affective mercy* (section 1). The second connection concerns the notion that emotional experience involves a sense of vulnerability such that the latter is a dimension of the former (section 2). The third connection concerns the notion that feeling vulnerable is typically not a neutral but a deeply affective experience (section 4). After having described these three connections, I explore their interplay and further illustrate them in the context of vulnerable narcissism, arguing that the notions developed are helpful in characterizing it (section 5).

1. The First Connection: Dependency on Affective Mercy

In this section, I'll begin with the first connection. First, it is helpful to examine the situations in which we tend to become emotional. We don't need to advocate a particular theory of emotion for this. To consider the abundance of approaches to affective experience would distract from the rather broadly shared understanding that emotions occur when our interests are affected in some sense through a given situation.¹ This can be expressed by saying that, in emotions and affective experience more broadly, we are aware of significance—of what matters to us, of what we value or desire, of the cares and concerns that arise—and to what extent we understand how all these are realized, fulfilled, or threatened in a given situation. Emphasizing that emotions occur when we realize that what we are

¹ For an overview of some of the main strands in the theory of emotion, see Reisenzein und Schmidt (2022).

striving for is affected by certain circumstances, doesn't commit us to any particular interpretation of *how* exactly we are aware of this—i.e., whether the original mode of awareness is perception, judgement, volition or motivation, feeling, bodily-kinaesthetic, attentional, a combination of these, or something else. The intention here is not to give a precise account of the nature of emotion or take sides in the debate within the philosophy of emotion. My point is rather that no matter how we end up theorizing about emotion, it will necessarily involve some conceptualization of the ways we are or find ourselves related to the *fact* that something of what we take to be a good can be attained or not.²

Such fact, as this formulation reveals, is made by two components: first, that we aim for something and take it as a good, and, second, that it is available or not. Of course, availability is typically not absolute: something may be unavailable under the given circumstances but could be accessible if the difficulties are overcome; something may be available only in the future but not yet, and so on. To give their intertwinement a name or slogan, I propose that emotions are *modal experiences of value*: they are an awareness of whether what is valuable for us is possible, impossible, necessary, certainly or likely to be realized, ought-to-be realized, allowed, expected or sought to be realized. Again, by this, I explicitly do not intend to provide a grand theory of emotions that explicates everything essential about all the emotions. In fact, I follow what could be called Solomon's verdict that he reached after ardently defending a cognitive theory of emotions for decades: "The enormous range of emotions suggests that no single claim or analysis will suit all emotions, or *emotion as such*." (Solomon 2003, 196)

In fact, by speaking of emotions as modal experiences of value, we would still need to examine the different kind of modalities prominent in a given kind of emotion case by case, which would allow for different theories fitting to some emotions better than others. To explain this only very briefly: Drawing from linguistics (Palmer 2001), we can roughly distinguish between epistemic, deontic, and dynamic modalities. Against this backdrop, we can say that some emotions

² Note that by 'fact' I do not exclusively refer to something simply being the case and our awareness of it, which would ultimately amount to a cognitive view of emotion. Instead, I also include a meaning of 'fact' that refers to the etymological Latin root of 'facere' (*to make*), arguing that sometimes it is our emotion itself that has made it that we deem a good to be attainable or not. For instance, my feeling disappointed or wronged by a friend can make it impossible for me to call them back or answer a text message.

may have a stronger epistemic focus and are more concerned with the knowledge or the knowledge process that concerns whether something of value will be realized or not. This is the case, for instance, when we fearfully ruminate about our partner potentially leaving us. Other emotions may be more concerned with deontic modalities, developing feelings that focus us on what we should do, what should have been done, how one should react to the situation, or how one could—morally speaking—act under the given circumstances. Yet other emotions may be best described by referring to dynamic modalities such that, in emotion, we predominantly feel motivated for and moved towards certain actions, because not only do we take ourselves to be able and capable of engaging in it, but also, through emotions such as joy, generosity, love, want to do so.

Referring to emotions as modal experiences, thus, allows us to refrain from reducing emotions to perceptual, cognitive, or motivational states—to name just a few prominent candidates, which I assume to be more apt to describe an emotion rather than the others, depending on which of the modalities is prominent in the emotion at stake. But all of this would require more work, which I omit here to instead focus on how understanding emotions as modal experiences helps us to capture the deep connection between emotion and experience of vulnerability that I want to elucidate.

For this I would like to take a look at the two components—in short, value and availability—through the lens of control, or stoically put, to what degree they are ‘up to us’ (*eph’ hemin*). My focus will be on the first though, as it seems obvious that regarding the availability of goods, much hinges on things in the world and other people rather than on our doings, even though we do, of course, have a say in our fate and the destiny of the world. I surely don’t have to point out how little our influence in this regard is though.

So, let’s focus on value and our sense of it. It is evident that the matter allows again for a plethora of views of subtle differences. The Stoic approach to emotion is paradigmatic for the idea that we are, at least in principle, free to control our emotions before they grow from affective impulses into full-fledged emotions by steering what we take to be a value. In fact, most of the Stoic advice regarding the prevention of emotion consists in meditating on and calibrating what we

appreciate and value. In today's times, Sartre and later Solomon have advocated the view that *choice* plays a central role in the development of emotional experience (Sartre 1956, 1993, Solomon 2003). However, as Solomon ultimately concedes, his "early emphasis on action and choice was misleading" because he "ignored or gerrymandered the many differences and distinctions ... and tried to defend a thesis about emotions *simpliciter*" (Solomon 2003, 197). Yet, while his late view was that each emotion requires an own analysis, he suggested that, "as a general strategy", we should "push the idea that we choose and are responsible for our emotions" (Solomon 2003, 198). The point is that it matters how we think about and assess our possibilities to regulate emotions and that considering ourselves helpless when we are struck by emotion may well make us more passive than we actually are (cf. Ford & Gross 2019).

I therefore believe that the older Solomon's general strategy is well-placed. Moreover, I venture that at least most of us make diverse experiences of significance and our abilities to change what we feel matters to us. Not everything we consider important in a given moment is written in stone, and our reflection, thoughts, and intentions may well help altering our perception of what we seemingly deem indispensable. What appears to us as mattering is in constant motion. Some of the things, certain relationships, moral principles, goals etc. may only change very slowly or even remain the same during our lives. But surely there are things that we took to be valuable and later became indifferent to. It happens all the time. But it doesn't always just *happen*. We often work towards caring less about certain people, things, ideas, or projects, and when we achieve it we do have a sense of having transformed ourselves and the axiological architecture that holds together our identity. It *feels* like an achievement rather than an occurrence. Of course, there also things we feel we cannot change without betraying severely who we are, while knowing that it would generally be possible to attain a different view. Consider, for instance, the sentence "Here I stand, I can do no other" that has been ascribed to Martin Luther when he was asked to give up his ideas for reformation at the Reichstag in Worms in 1521. In other cases, we would like to change who we are but, to no avail, we don't yield the desired evaluative position and despite all attempts we still feel affection for something

or someone. We can certainly aim for feeling differently about a certain thing and try to appreciate it or stop doing so, but in the end, we remain dependent on the corresponding feeling to occur. Accordingly, we don't have absolute power over our value-feelings but only "profective (*profektiv*)" power, as the phenomenologist Hans Reiner (1927, 39) called it. To put it poignantly: Unlike the Stoics claim, it is *not fully up to us* how we value things but *we can do something about* and *for it* to evoke the right felt value in us, while we always need to remain hopeful that our efforts be crowned with success.³

The hope that typically arises when we try to attune ourselves to values we wish to identify with shows that, however much agency we exercise in shaping our axiological mindset, there always remains an element of exposure to what lies beyond our control—an exposure requiring patience and implying a passivity that, strictly speaking, we remain reliant on even *in* our activity.

This point can be further exemplified through a look in the field of the history of emotions. In Christian theology and the related theories of emotion as well as in the practical lives in monasteries, from medieval times up to reformation, clerical thinkers and monks were concerned about generating the right feelings, were craving for sentiments of connection, love, generosity, and spiritual fulfilment to feel close to God. If Christian theology warned against many sinful affects, it always also propagated the development of a broad set of other feelings. In these contexts, not being able to evoke the right feelings was the spectre of *acedia*, a form of Christian depression and affective detachment. Christian thinkers were eager to discover the proper means—including diets, sleep practices, and spiritual rituals (Dixon 2003)—that would result in the right sentiments to arise. Despite all these activities, it was understood that yielding the desired affective constitution was ultimately a question of God's grace, even if it did require agency and action on the side of the individual.

³ Some may object that the same applies to bodily motion and that, when we try to lift our arm, we also have to wait for the corresponding behaviour to occur. But in my view there is a phenomenological difference, as we simply move our arm if we are not hindered by internal or external reasons. In the case of a transformation of felt value, motion is typically temporally extended to a significant degree and includes waiting and allows for prediction and probability. This is reflected in situations in which we say things like 'I am not sure yet whether I will be able to let go of this idea, I'll try'.

From a mundane or more existentialist view, we could call such a dependency *affective mercy*⁴, which also implies that we remain, as long as we enact our affective lives, vulnerable to something we end up not being able to control.⁵ This exposition need not be to some strict exteriority, but may instead be to our very own self—appearing to us as at once familiar and strange in reflection, something we would like to change but oddly find ourselves incapable to do.

2. The Second Connection: The Sense of Vulnerability in Emotional Experience

So far, I have argued that emotional experience carries in itself a passive moment even when we enact emotion. By this, I was first and foremost referring to the *conditions* of affective life rather than its phenomenal texture. I now focus on the latter and explore the qualities of emotional experience and how a sense of vulnerability may be involved in it. To anticipate, I will develop the view that all emotional experience, in some way, involves a sense of vulnerability. This does not amount to the claim that any emotion is *about* or primarily concerned with vulnerability. Instead, the more modest assumption would be that a sense of vulnerability features in any emotion, shaping what kind of emotion and how we experience it. It takes it as a defining *aspect* of emotional experience, among others. I propose that this is a direct implication of understanding emotions as modal experiences of value, as I have suggested in the last section. This is so because emotions, according to this view, though in very diverse ways, are all concerned with the realization of what we take to be valuable. And, as I have emphasized, this involves two fundamental forms of vulnerabilities: affective mercy and insecure availability of the sought-for-goods.

It is relatively easy to illustrate that when the goods we strive for are unavailable that we get emotional in different ways: anxiety or fear, hope, anger, or sadness are all clear emotive ways of relating to a good's accessibility, which can involve

⁴ The meaning I give the term differs from and is not related to how it has been used elsewhere: as the idea that mercy as a virtue in the Christian person has two aspects, an effective and affective one (Daniel & Harris 2024, 4264).

⁵ The much-discussed phenomenon of „recalcitrant emotions“ (e.g., Döring 2015) is a good example for cases in which an individual is not blessed by affective mercy.

different modal activities—understood in a broad sense—such as assuming that availability is likely or unlikely, wanting to make it available, accepting its impossibility, and so on. In this sense, it seems obvious that anxiety, fear, hope and sadness involve a sense of being exposed to something that is not in our hands. However, it is not immediately obvious how the same applies to throughout positive emotions involving exuberant joy or excitement. These occur when we are happy about a situation because something we appreciate has been or is about to be realized.⁶ And yet, it is also the celebratory feelings of fulfilment that reveal a reference to vulnerability. For, it is precisely the—if only punctual—overcoming of the latter that occasions the delight with a situation. This is expressed, for instance, in utterances like “Incredible!”, “It’s really happening.”, “Who would have thought?” In joy, the enjoyment is partly constituted through the sense that something became real that was possible, perhaps even unlikely, but surely not necessary, and thus nothing we could have taken for granted. It is also for this reason that we can feel throughout grateful and gifted, even in the things to the achievement of which we have greatly contributed. We are thankful because they could have turned out very differently and we are aware that, apart from our influence, an abundance of factors that are not in our hands have defined the situation in question. Consider also the emotional experience when we feel the warmth and sense of belonging when we are with people we love and like—friends, family, loved ones. Although related emotions may not be about vulnerability, we still have an implicit sense of it, insofar as we enjoy precisely the feeling of being safe, sheltered, and emotionally protected. A sense of vulnerability is also involved in emotions that are self-related and that concern an evaluation of one’s achievement and the activities that led to it, for instance, pride. In many cases of pride, we can be very much aware of our vulnerabilities. We celebrate the fact that we could—despite the obstacles, attacks, or dangers—yield what we were aiming for. The sense of ability in pride doesn’t silence the specter

⁶ My thoughts presented here concerning happiness—but also regarding the understanding of emotions as modal experiences of value—are significantly influenced by Stephan Strasser’s account in his *Phenomenology of Feelings* (1977) and his interpretation of Thomas Aquinas’ theory of the passions. For a more text-oriented interpretation see Schmidt (2023) and Klein and Schmidt (2024).

of vulnerability completely, it rather derives its precise meaning against the backdrop of it.

This brings me to a more general point I wish to emphasize. I am pushing the idea that all emotions as modal experiences of values feature *some* sense of vulnerability. However, in doing so, I am not trumpeting for a purely passive interpretation of emotions that has often been defended in the history of philosophy when—certain— affective experiences were conceptualized as *pathē* or passions at all. Following Solomon (2003), I believe that every emotional experience bears active and passive moments, the distribution of which significantly contributes to which shape our feelings take.

Consider the sense of ability being an essential aspect to emotional experience in general (Slaby 2012, Slaby & Wüschner 2014).⁷ I very much concur with this idea and have also argued that we should bear in mind the deeper entanglement between emotion and our agency elsewhere (Schmidt-Boddy under review, Schmidt-Boddy & Fuchs under review a, b, Fuchs & Schmidt-Boddy under review).⁸

But here I want to underscore that our sense of ability and vulnerability are two sides of the same coin. Both together form an irreducible phenomenon: our abilities are always encircled by boundaries, limitations, and uncontrollable processes. In fact, many practical skills involve the expertise and knowledge when a “window” opens, and an action becomes possible. The temporal structure of our practical endeavours follows to a great deal the principle of *kairos*, which Heidegger famously described in *Being and Time* (1927) and argued to be primordial to any chronological understanding of time. The idea of *kairos* revolves around the notions of chance and occasion, betraying also that certain things are only possible if done at the proper time. This implies an understanding of one’s own control as circumstantial and depending on external factors. Our abilities, thus, are not to be absolutely separated from our vulnerabilities. They are the ways in which we navigate vulnerabilities and the lack of control we are confronted with in this world on a daily basis. My point then is that our emotional

⁷ See also Slaby’s chapter in this volume.

⁸ Compare Colombetti (2014) or Naar (2024) for other takes on the intricacies between emotion and agency.

experience is shot through with both a sense of what we are capable of achieving in the world and what we aren't.

3. Brief Stoic Intermezzo

The insight that all emotional experience, in some way, involves a sense of vulnerability is precisely the reason why the Stoics argued we should prevent passions from arising in the first place. I have already emphasized that the notion of affective mercy implies that the Stoic proposal is psychologically unfeasible, at least in its extreme variant. Nonetheless I take it to contain interesting ideas that inform my approach. First, it is necessary to see that the Stoics didn't suggest extinguishing all affective experiences but just one kind: passion or *pathē*.⁹ This also means that getting rid of the passions would result in a state of *apatheia* but not in a mindset bereft of all affective experience. In fact, reaching this state of the Sage would allow an individual to feel reasonable joy (*chará*) instead of pleasure (*hēdonē*), volition (*boulēsis*) instead of desire (*epithymía*), and caution (*eulábeia*) instead of fear (*phóbos*), which are all affective experiences relating to one's moral agency rather than the (for us unchangeable) facts of the world and other people. However, as I would argue, the Stoics also know an affective experience that relates to our being exposed to nature (including our body) and other people. It's just that it is of a non-pathic kind and not listed as a feeling but as a good. For instance, Seneca writes that security is what constitutes the good life of the Stoic sage: "cum summa vitae beatae sit solida securitas et eius inconcussa fiducia" (Seneca, Epistula XLIV, 7). And, it is only the Stoic who can achieve this state: "(S)ecuritas autem proprium bonum sapientis est(.)" (Seneca, De Constantia sapientis, 13,5). Once a person has reached this stage, they can't even undergo any wrongdoing—the Stoic Sage is in this sense *invulnerable*, because whatever happens it will not affect *them* as individuals purely living in their moral agency (Seneca, De Constantia sapientis, 10,3). Because the Stoic sage

⁹ As Dixon (2003) rightly points out, it is problematic to apply the notion of emotions to historical approaches without further qualification. The Stoics didn't know the notion of 'emotion', which is an invention of modern times. For the Stoics, there existed different affective experiences including the passions, which corresponds the most to what we'd call emotions today.

is a-pathic, he cannot be touched by the events in the world, and this allows them to engage in the good affective motions that I mentioned, the *eupathieai*. They can direct their concern fully on their moral agency. The Stoic's good spirit (*eudaimon*), then, is owing to the absence of worry. In other words, the Stoic happy life involves a sense of vulnerability, one in which vulnerability has been absolutely transcended and overcome for good. The Stoic peace of mind is an ideal modification of our sense of vulnerability. And as such it is a version of affective life, not its denial but a transformation of it towards joyful tranquillity—not the absence of feeling but one of its modes, which we might be best described as an “existential feeling” (Ratcliffe 2005).

The point is that, while it seems psychologically impossible to reach such a state, as an *ideal* mode of feeling, in which any possibility is experienced as non-threatening, it is fully conceivable. And, because this is so, we can learn from the insights of the Stoics analyses of its phenomenal aspects. I would like to draw attention to the following ideas that I will further develop and modify in my own approach. The first is that how we experience vulnerability is a question of how we enact our affective life, and that, accordingly, our abilities to prevent, control, and regulate certain emotions are relevant in this regard. Second, that it is absolute trust (*fiducia inconcussa*) in security that provides a feeling of invulnerability. Whether such kind of unshakable trust can be realized or not is one thing, but the important thought is that our trust practices may transform our *felt* sense of vulnerability. The Stoics believe that the decision is made between emotional life (*pathē*) and a feeling of invulnerability (*apatheia*). By contrast, I think the opposition is rather between emotional life with a varying sense of vulnerability that is never—at least not in a non-delusional way—turned into *absolute* invulnerability on the one hand and explicit feelings of being vulnerable on the other. I will describe these briefly in the following section, before I further explore the role of emotional abilities and trust in their development and sustainment.

4. The Third Connection: Feeling Vulnerable

I have argued that emotional experience always involves a sense of our vulnerabilities. However, by this I didn't say that we necessarily feel vulnerable in an explicit sense, as many emotions are not *about* being vulnerable. It is not that in having an emotion per se, we *suffer* the pains of being vulnerable. It is only in some cases that vulnerability becomes the centre of our emotional concern and that our sufferings revolve thematically around exposition and the limitations of our control.

Take, for instance, emotional experiences in the context of psychopathology, which are typically difficult to control. Anxieties, depressive affects, feelings of loneliness, and other affective experiences that can arise in psychopathology usually have their own themes and objects. However, they all share that individuals normally also develop a sense of being exposed to these affective processes accompanied by very limited hopes for being able to regain control when they occur. It is under these conditions that explicit feelings of being vulnerable may and often arise. As Fuchs (2013) argues, it is precisely in psychopathology that individuals tend to develop feelings of vulnerability even in situations that are relatively inconspicuous by triggering emotions that are concerned—pre-reflectively or reflectively—with the existential conditions of human life. These have an antinomical structure, as Fuchs suggests following Jaspers, and include aspects such as freedom and possibility but also finiteness, boundaries, and fragility.¹⁰ He labels this heightened sensitivity towards feeling exposed to these basic facts of human life *existential vulnerability*.

While I agree that all psychopathologies relate to these basic facts in some way and come with a feeling of vulnerability, it's important not to overlook that its phenomenology can still look quite differently across mental health conditions. The *felt* vulnerability in the case of a person with panic attacks will feel differently exposed to the process of anxieties than an individual with borderline personality disorder where fears revolve around abandonment or low self-esteem, although both cases may refer, on an abstract level, to a loss of control. What I want to suggest therefore is that feelings of vulnerability, in their phenomenal structure

¹⁰ Despite this link between psychopathology and vulnerability, it should be noted that experiences of vulnerability can also have a moralpsychological value by being an indispensable element in the self-understanding of our practical identities (Bizarri 2023).

and meaning, are shaped by the contexts in and through which they arise as well as by the ways an individual tries to navigate and regulate them, i.e., how a person *enacts* feelings of vulnerability. In the final section, I explore the role of emotional abilities in the enaction of vulnerability and how they mould our feelings of vulnerability. To do so, I focus on a paradigmatic example: vulnerable narcissism.

5. Emotional Abilities in Vulnerable Narcissism

In the previous sections, I have shed light on three connections between emotional life and vulnerability. In all of them, emotional abilities play a central role. First, I argued that all our emotional life is characterized by affective mercy, remaining reliant on the attempts we engage in to shape our feelings being successful. Second, I argued that all emotional experiences feature a varying sense of vulnerability that also depends on the goods we aim to attain and the outlook of their availability for us. Third, I suggested that an explicit feeling vulnerable may develop if we can't yield the feelings we aim for. This maybe because we are not graced with affective mercy or we consent to values that are important for us but cannot be realized.

I now turn to vulnerable narcissism as an example. There are good reasons for addressing vulnerable narcissism. Vulnerable narcissists are prone to develop severe feelings of vulnerability, which are at the heart of other psychological and behavioural tendencies. They also show increased difficulties with emotion regulation, which is one of the aspects that distinguishes them from grandiose narcissism (Underwood et al. 2021). As I suggest, it is precisely the way vulnerable narcissists enact their vulnerability that makes them even more vulnerable in the long run, showcasing how emotional abilities feed back into how our vulnerabilities are manifest as affective experiences.

Vulnerable narcissism, then, is a paradigmatic example because it is mostly about different kinds of felt vulnerabilities and their continuous sustainment and reproduction through the way they are navigated. I mainly want to do two things: First, I want to sketch phenomenologically the characteristics of the feelings of vulnerability that drive the vulnerable narcissists' engagements with the world;

second, I want to describe the ways in which vulnerable narcissists deal with their feelings of vulnerability and how these practices and the emotional abilities implied nourish rather than dissolve feelings of vulnerability. My analysis is not exhaustive but exemplary. I hope to ignite further discussion in philosophical psychology on vulnerable narcissism, which has so far not received the kind of attention given to grandiose narcissism—the latter being, by and large, the more prominent face of narcissism.

Vulnerable narcissism: entitlement, diminished sense of agency, and victimhood

It's much more difficult to spot vulnerable narcissism in a person than grandiosity that is openly displayed and that can lead to direct conflict if not mirrored in the way needed by the narcissistic person. Vulnerable narcissists, by contrast, often seem charming, considerate, and evoke sympathy in others. And yet, they share significant aspects with grandiose narcissists in experiencing the need to be met with external validation as well as a feeling of entitlement.

But the vulnerable subtype is far from being only a simply covert or hidden version of narcissism. It has its own experiential and behavioural signature.

For instance, it has been observed that entitlement in vulnerable narcissism is based on a concern of injustice. Vulnerable narcissists feel entitled to gain attention and support because they believe they have been wronged, whereas grandiose narcissists' entitlement is derived from a sense of superiority (Freis & Hansen-Brown 2021).

Other studies have observed that vulnerable narcissism is associated especially with shame, envy, more depression, more anger and hostility, and much lower self-esteem than grandiose narcissists; they are more introverted, anxious, and avoidant (Weinberg & Ronningstam 2022, Braun et al. 2024, Krizan & Johar 2012). They show an “explosive mix of mistrust, anger, and shame as core ingredients of narcissistic rage” (Krizan & Johan 2015, 784).

They tend towards hostile attribution (Hansen-Brown & Freis 2019), although they also generally attribute the outcome of situations internally, which has been linked to the vast feelings of shame they suffer from (Braun et al. 2024). An

individual may then tend to ascribe malignant motives to others while feeling there is a feature of themselves that explains the discomfiting situation.

Accordingly, vulnerable narcissists have a higher risk of feeling rejected, triggering their fears of abandonment, which have been identified as a key theme (Green et al. 2019). In comparison to the fears of abandonment often related to borderline personality disorder, however, in the context of vulnerable narcissism, they are concerned more with social status rather than interpersonal connection. That is, the fear of abandonment is mostly about the narcissistic supply and the external validation others may provide.

Vulnerable and grandiose narcissism, thus, have also been conceptualized as “alternative status-seeking strategies” with the former being identified with a “dove” strategy that consists in “entering low-stakes contents and competing against weak opponents for low payoffs” (Mahadevan 2024, 5f.). Unlike grandiose narcissists who often show skills in controlling their emotions and their expressions, vulnerable narcissists have difficulties with emotion regulation (Underwood et al. 2021), and it is probably therefore that they prefer less-risk scenarios with subtle and indirect contests and antagonism—including passive-aggressive behaviour rather than direct conflict.

A recurring theme in the discussions is a victimhood mentality that has been associated with vulnerable narcissism. Related feelings of being wronged and victimized may correspond to shame, envy, and the disappointment of narcissistic demands for external validation. These high demands rarely met and thus readily give to feelings of incapacity in realizing what a person values. It has been argued that this explains the low or lack of a sense of agency observed in vulnerable narcissists (but not in grandiose narcissists) (Brown et al. 2016, Hansen-Brown 2018). Victimhood mentality and *playing the victim* has also been described as a strategy to regulate and ignite narcissistic supply. “Once in victim mode they are emotionally persuasive way beyond the ability of a neurotypical person”, says Lorna Slade (as cited in Briscoe 2021), a psychotherapist focusing on healing from narcissistic abuse, in an interview with *The Guardian*. Victim signalling, the “public and intentional expression of one’s disadvantages, suffering, oppression, or personal limitations” (Ok et al. 2021, 1635) is therefore also considered to be

a so-called *resource transfer strategy*, where the vulnerable narcissist self-victimizes to immunize against “claims on their own moral transgressions” or for “strategic manipulation of non-victims, designed to elicit a transfer of resources from the non-victims to the victim signaller” (Bates et al. 2025, 1).

Affective mercy, emotional experience, and feelings of vulnerability in narcissism

After sketching vulnerable narcissism, I would like to illustrate the interplay between affective mercy, the implicit sense of vulnerability in emotional experience, and explicit feelings of vulnerability, and to show how these notions can help describe and conceptualize the specific forms and experiences of vulnerability that are characteristic of different mental health conditions. In what follows, I’ll propose an interpretation of the dynamic experience of vulnerability in narcissism.

I begin with a discussion of the explicit feeling of vulnerability. As I have argued above, feelings of vulnerability vary in their specific *how* with the contexts that trigger them and should not be considered as if a fixed quale. Feelings of vulnerability are determined by what one takes oneself to be exposed to, what one believes to be under threat, and the perceived means of control, i.e., the ways one can affect the extent to which one’s values are realized and protected. In what follows, I propose an interpretation of the situation in vulnerable narcissism.

In the case of vulnerable narcissism, it became evident that self-esteem is of central concern and under permanent threat. In vulnerable narcissism, two aspects of affective experience are connected with this pervasive concern. First, the incapacity to generate a feeling of self-worth on one’s own. I mentioned that affective mercy adheres to our emotional life in general, but that it is only *felt* when we’d like to change how we feel but seem incapable of doing so. Vulnerable narcissism is such an example, where a person’s sense of self-esteem is chronically impeded and does not follow the desire for regulation, as most attempts to invoke a more self-appreciative affective stance are unsuccessful. Second, vulnerable narcissists seem to develop a temporary sense of self-esteem

when their demands for their desired treatments through others are met with attention, which provides them with external validation.

The etiological background of vulnerable narcissism and the described affective constellation has still not been fully unveiled, but there is evidence that this narcissistic subtype is more associated with adverse events and early childhood trauma, including verbal, emotional, or physical abuse, coldness, and overcontrol by caretakers (Miller et al. 2017). The foundation of vulnerable narcissism seems to be a pervasive or severe experience of being determined by others, in a way that didn't allow for the person to develop a satisfying sense of agency in the interaction with the caretaker or significant others. The abiding experiential basis of vulnerable narcissists, then, is a form of felt passivity and exposition. Insofar as others are experienced as the centre of control, what I want to suggest happens is that two things in the emotional experience of the vulnerable narcissist merge: the perception of affective mercy within the context of one's attempts to regulate emotion and the perception of other people as the locus of control. In other words, the sense of not being able to control one's emotions and the sense of dependency on others get linked and intertwined. The inability of self-determined emotional self-regulation and dependency on others becomes the same thing. Affective mercy or its absence is perceived as defined and decided *by others*.

That means that a vulnerable narcissist perceives their emotional life as—almost immediately, as it were—tied to the way relevant people interact and treat the narcissist. This fact alone, in my view, will account for low self-esteem, lack of self-confidence, diminished sense of agency, and the shame so quickly felt that propels narcissistic rage if the relevant other doesn't show the desired treatment and fails to provide narcissistic supply. It has been observed that failure in the self-regulatory attempts to stop caring about other people's feedback results in even greater levels of shame (Freis et al. 2015). This constellation also explains the tendency to blame others and to feel wronged: if others are seen as controlling one's emotional life, negative affect is taken as their fault—perhaps even as intended. Moreover, I suggest that even positive emotions, because they carry an implicit sense of vulnerability, may easily irritate vulnerable narcissists because it can trigger the same discomforting feelings of dependency on others and lack of

affective self-determination. I think this may in part explain the ambivalent relationships vulnerable narcissists can often entertain even with those people that do bolster their self-esteem and provide the kind of narcissistic supply that would allow them to feel comfortable and develop positive emotions. But with the latter comes the bitter felt sense that one's feelings of joy, hope, or warmth are owing to the grace of the other person. This is the reason why I believe no narcissistic supply whatsoever could provide the security the vulnerable narcissist would need.

Their vulnerability, in fact, has precisely the opposite character of the mindset of the Stoic sage, whose security and absolute trust in the world makes them invulnerable to any emotional injury through others. If the Stoic sage 'lives in' his sense of agency and focuses on what is up to them, the vulnerable narcissists can never fully feel secure, trusting, and live in what is up to them. In stark contrast to the Stoic sage, the vulnerable narcissist can and frequently gets emotionally injured over *anything*. This is a permanent threat that is felt even when things may run smoothly for some time. And even when it does, because the dependency on others is never really forgotten, the vulnerable narcissist will feel undermined in their emotional autonomy. Being pleased through the treatment of others confirms dependency on others, just as does negative affect that is interpreted as being the result of others' actions.

Narcissistic enactment of vulnerability and its perpetuation: Three tendencies

The kind of vulnerability felt in these cases, then, is mainly concerned with one's own emotional life and its processes, the sense of agency featuring in it, and the central role of other people therein. To conclude the paper, I finally describe some aspects of the way how narcissists enact this kind of vulnerability, and how these forms of navigating feeling ultimately lead to the sustainment of a non-abiding vulnerability in the long run.

I focus on three interrelated tendencies that I take to be active in vulnerable narcissists as responses to the fundamental dynamics of felt vulnerability that I described. I am hesitant to call them strategies because I understand them as

adaptations on different levels that concern styles in perception, cognition, feeling, volition, and behaviour—which may also involve different strategies.

The first tendency concerns attempts to *instigate what could be called a compensatory sense of agency* within the interaction with others in order to mitigate feelings of dependency, exposition, and passivity. In accordance with the mentioned dove-strategy, vulnerable narcissists seek to express and negotiate narcissistic shame over lack of control by evoking little stitches in the self-esteem or affective life of others. The petty little conflicts that can emerge in these contexts are known to most who have dealt with narcissists: antagonism about literally nothing where the only—rather abstract and formal—goal is to renegotiate power distributions, for instance, complex, long, and unnecessary discussions about who should be the first one to contact the other for a dinner meeting. Antagonism, mixed with desire for revenge, can also include sabotaging projects of others or making them more difficult than necessary in order to reassure oneself that one is the main or at least central author of a situation. It can also include subtle attempts to exclude certain others from group decision processes by sharing information only to selected members of the group or setting appointments where people to be excluded cannot be presented.

The second tendency concerns attempts (and the underlying desire) to *control other people*. If a person perceives their emotional life as dependent on the actions of others and they feel they can't control themselves directly, it is easy to see how this may motivate a person to exert self-control indirectly by influencing the others. To get the desired treatment by others, vulnerable narcissists may engage in different ways of manipulation to make sure the others are nudged in the right way (Casale et al. 2019).

The third tendency concerns the *objectification of others*. R. D. Laing has described how a lack of basic security in schizophrenia, “ontological insecurity” (Laing 1965, 39ff.), can lead to an anxiety of being depersonalized and reified by others. Laing refers to Sartre's famous shame analysis in *Being and Nothingness* and describes this fear of being no more than a mere thing to others, of being turned into an object for the other as a subject. As a consequence, to prevent such a terrifying experience, Laing describes a kind of manoeuvre that would reverse

roles: “(H)e turned the other person into a thing in his own eyes, thus magically nullifying any danger to himself by secretly totally disarming the enemy; (b)y destroying, in his own eyes, the other person as a person, he robbed the other of his power to crush him.” (Laing 1965, 48) Although the conditions of schizophrenia are significantly different to narcissism, I propose that a somewhat similar coping mechanism can be identified in vulnerable narcissism: because individuals feel themselves subjected to the evaluative judgments of others (and thus objectified), they begin to objectify others by preventively judging about them. This can take the form of “*a* is *x* or *y*” but it can also occur in terms of narrative fixation “*a* has done *x* or *y*” or “because *a* has done *x* or *y*, I did *z*”. If vulnerable narcissists do not sufficiently feel as the authors of their situation, they may engage in attempts to compensate for this by trying to become the narrator of the situation. In other words, when they feel agentially determined and dominated by others, they may tend to try to domesticate the other by exerting narrative control. Narratives may take the function of what Karl Jaspers (2019, 143) called a “housing” or “shell“ (*Gehäuse*), an interpretation of the world through which the person can feel at home in their situation and develop a sense of security. While this may often be primarily a means to develop more favourable self-views, it can also manifest as a manipulation tactic within the relevant social contexts. Trying to establish a certain narrative before others may reduce and undermine the possibilities of selected others and thus alters interaction indirectly. A commentator on an educational video on Youtube by Ramani Durvasula, a psychologist focusing on narcissism, expresses this principle well: “Yep, and if they can’t control you, they’ll try to control how other people see you.”¹¹

By acting out any combination of these tendencies, vulnerable narcissists can have tremendous effects on others and on the shape social environments take. However, while such enactment of vulnerability may at times achieves to paper over the vast feelings of vulnerability, passivity and victimhood, the latter will typically resurface eventually. This is not the least the case because acting out these tendencies typically creates new vulnerabilities that perpetuate the situation. First, narcissistic antagonism and the destructive behaviours that ensue will often

¹¹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=d5VtTHFnkXk&t=309s>

trigger some reactions in others that will, in the end, lead to conflict and even less external validation. Second, the need or even obsession to control other people translates into a desire that is difficult to fulfil, as even the most submissive person, unless under tyrannic domination, will likely betray some individual freedom in their actions, which presents a constant source of irritation for the vulnerable narcissist. Third, the same applies to any attempt of objectifying other people. Any indication of the to-be-objectified and narratively to-be-controlled subject's successful resistance will create a threat to the individual that feels the need to psychologically fixate the other person.

Accordingly, the narcissistic enactment of vulnerability is futile. While its desperate measures to instigate some sense of agency may temporarily work, it perpetuates its own suffering in the long run. Contrary to what the vulnerable narcissists feel, it is *primarily* up to the narcissist to stop the much-discussed *shame-rage spiral* (Lewis 1971, Scheff 1987) and their psychological dependency on others. It's admittedly very difficult without affective mercy on one's side. But if I have joined the critics on the Stoics for being too optimistic about one's ability to mould one's affective life, I would be similarly hesitant to accept that there is nothing we could do about it.

Conclusion

In this chapter, I aimed to illustrate three connections between vulnerability and emotions. I first described the general vulnerability of our emotional life that I termed affective mercy: even if we can do something to shape our affective experiences, we remain dependent on these attempts being ultimately successful. Typically, we only become aware of the relevance of affective mercy when we make attempts to modify emotions or affective experiences of value but seem unable to do so. I then proposed the view that emotions are modal experiences of value that all feature an implicit and varying sense of vulnerability, even when we are happy and full of joy such that some sense of vulnerability is, at least tacitly, present in most, if not all, experiences of the world. I then discussed explicit feelings of vulnerability which are shaped by the contexts in which they arise and

in which vulnerability is thematic in one way or another. In the last section, I applied these notions to the case of vulnerable narcissism and used them to elucidate not only the feelings of vulnerability characteristic of related mental health conditions but also the ways in which vulnerable narcissists enact their felt vulnerability and how they feed back into a pervasive experience of vulnerability before other people. Doing so, my aim was to illustrate the central importance of our emotional abilities and their impact on how we experience vulnerability emotionally.

References

Bates, T. C., Grant, C., Hobbs, L., Johnston, C., Moghaddam, S., & Sinclair, K. (2025). Virtuous victimhood as a Dark Triad resource transfer strategy. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 234, 112964. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2024.112964>

Bizzari, V. (2023). The ontological and ethical value of vulnerability: A reflection between phenomenology and psychopathology. In E. Boublil & S. Ferrarello (Eds.), *The vulnerability of the human world (Philosophy and Medicine, Vol. 148, pp. 49–62)*. Cham: Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-41824-2_4

Braun, S., Schyns, B., Zheng, Y., & [et al.]. (2024). When vulnerable narcissists take the lead: The role of internal attribution of failure and shame for abusive supervision. *Journal of Business Ethics*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-024-05805-w>

Briscoe, J. (2021). Not all narcissists are grandiose – the ‘vulnerable’ type can be just as dangerous. *The Guardian*. Retrieved from <https://www.theguardian.com/lifeandstyle/2021/aug/01/not-all-narcissists-are-grandiose-the-vulnerable-type-can-be-just-as-dangerous>

Brown, A. A., Freis, S. D., Carroll, P. J., & Arkin, R. M. (2016). Perceived agency mediates the link between the narcissistic subtypes and self-esteem. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 90, 124–129. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2015.10.055>

Cain, N. M., Pincus, A. L., & Ansell, E. B. (2008). Narcissism at the crossroads: phenotypic description of pathological narcissism across clinical theory, social/personality psychology, and psychiatric diagnosis. *Clinical psychology review*, 28(4), 638–656. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpr.2007.09.006>

Casale, S., Rugai, L., Giangrasso, B., & Fioravanti, G. (2019). Trait-Emotional Intelligence and the Tendency to Emotionally Manipulate Others Among Grandiose and Vulnerable Narcissists. *The Journal of Psychology*, 153(4), 402–413. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00223980.2018.1564229>

Colombetti, G. (2014). *The feeling body: Affective science meets the enactive mind*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press. <https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/9780262019958.001.0001>

Daniel, O. & Harris, H. (2024). Intersections of compassion, science, and spiritual care in global health for public health benefits. *Journal of Religion and Health*, 63(7), 4257–4275. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10943-024-02145-x>

Day, N. J. S., Townsend, M. L., & Grenyer, B. F. S. (2020). Living with pathological narcissism: a qualitative study. *Borderline personality disorder and emotion dysregulation*, 7(1), 19. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40479-020-00132-8>

Dixon, T. (2003). *From Passions to Emotions. The Creation of a Secular Psychological Category*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

Döring, S. A. (2015). What's wrong with recalcitrant emotions? From irrationality to challenge of agential identity. *Dialectica*, 69(3), 381–402. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1746-8361.12109>

Ford, B. Q. & Gross, J. J. (2019). Why beliefs about emotion matter: An emotion-regulation perspective. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 28(1), 74–81. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0963721418806697>

Freis, S. D., Brown, A. A., Carroll, P. J., & Arkin, R. M. (2015). Shame, rage, and unsuccessful motivated reasoning in vulnerable narcissism. *Journal of Social and Clinical Psychology*, 34(10), 877–895.

Freis, S. D., & Hansen-Brown, A. A. (2021). Justifications of entitlement in grandiose and vulnerable narcissism: The roles of injustice and superiority. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 168, 110345. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2020.110345>

Fuchs T. (2013). Existential vulnerability: toward a psychopathology of limit situations. *Psychopathology*, 46(5), 301–308. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000351838>

Fuchs, T. & Schmidt-Boddy, P. (under review). Enactive affectivity and emotion regulation. OUP

Green, A., & Charles, K. (2019). Voicing the victims of narcissistic partners: A qualitative analysis of responses to narcissistic injury and self-esteem regulation. *SAGE Open*, 9(2). <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244019846693>

Hansen-Brown, A. A. (2018). Perceived control theory of narcissism. In A. D. Hermann, A. B. Brunell, & J. D. Foster (Eds.), *Handbook of trait narcissism: Key advances, research methods, and controversies* (pp. 27–35). Cham, Switzerland: Springer.

Hansen-Brown, A. A., & Freis, S. D. (2019). Assuming the worst: Hostile attribution bias in vulnerable narcissists. *Self and Identity*, 20(2), 152–164. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15298868.2019.1609574>

Husserl, E. (1973). *Ding und Raum. Vorlesungen 1907*. Den Haag: Martinus Nijhoff.

Jaspers, K. (2019). *Psychologie der Weltanschauungen*. Basel: Schwabe.

Klein, M. & Schmidt, P. (2024). Über Erfüllung. Genuss und Glück bei Stephan Strasser und Thomas von Aquin. *Deutsche Zeitschrift für Philosophie*, 72 (3), 413–431. <https://doi.org/10.1515/dzph-2024-0030>

Krizan, Z., & Johar, O. (2012). Envy divides the two faces of narcissism. *Journal of personality*, 80(5), 1415–1451. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-6494.2012.00767.x>

Krizan, Z., & Johar, O. (2015). Narcissistic rage revisited. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 108(5), 784–801. <https://doi.org/10.1037/pspp0000013>

Landweer, H. (2022). Emotionale Fähigkeiten: Aktive und implizite Steuerung von Gefühlen. *Deutsche Zeitschrift für Philosophie*, 70(6), 937–954. <https://doi.org/10.1515/dzph-2022-0065>

Laing, R. D. (1965). *The Divided Self. An Existential Study in Sanity and Madness*. Harmondworth a. o.: Penguin Books.

Lewis, H. B. (1971). *Shame and guilt in neurosis*. New York, NY: International Universities Press.

Mahadevan, N. (2024). Conceptualizing grandiose and vulnerable narcissism as alternative status-seeking strategies: Insights from hierometer theory. *Social and Personality Psychology Compass*, e12977. <https://doi.org/10.1111/spc3.12977>

Miller, J. D., Lynam, D. R., Hyatt, C. S., & Campbell, W. K. (2017). Controversies in narcissism. *Annual Review of Clinical Psychology*, 13, 291–315. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-clinpsy-032816-045244>

Naar, H. (2024). Emotions and the action analogy: Prospects for an agential theory of emotions. *Journal of the American Philosophical Association*, 10(1), 64–78. <https://doi.org/10.1017/apa.2023.11>

Ok, E., Qian, Y., Strejcek, B., & Aquino, K. (2021). Signaling virtuous victimhood as indicators of Dark Triad personalities. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 120(6), 1634–1661. <https://doi.org/10.1037/pspp0000329>

Palmer, F. R. (2001). *Mood and Modality*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

Reiner, H. (1927). *Freiheit, Wollen und Aktivität. Phänomenologische Untersuchungen in Richtung auf das Problem der Willensfreiheit*. Halle/Saale: Max Niemeyer.

Ratcliffe, M. (2008). *Feeling of Being. Phenomenology, Psychiatry, and the Sense of Reality*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

Reisenzein, R. & Schmidt, P. (2022). Emotional Feelings: Evaluative Perceptions or Position-Takings? Introduction to the Special Section. *Emotion Review*, 14 (4), 233–243.

Ryrie, A. (2013). *Being Protestant in Reformation Britain*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

Sartre, J. P. (1993). *The Emotions. Outline of a Theory*. New York: Citadel Press.

Sartre, J. P. (1956). *Being and Nothingness. A Phenomenological Essay on Ontology*. New York: Washington Square Press.

Scheff, T. J. (1987). The shame–rage spiral: A case study of an interminable quarrel. In H. B. Lewis (Ed.), *The role of shame in symptom formation* (pp. 109–149). Hillsdale, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.

Schmidt-Boddy, P. (under review). Emotional agency. Self-regulation and the affective makings of the world. OUP

Schmidt-Boddy, P. & Fuchs, T. (under review a). Introductory essay: Perspectives on the phenomenology of emotion regulation. OUP

Schmidt-Boddy, P. & Fuchs, T. (under review b). Affective self-regulation and lived experience in psychopathology. OUP

Schmidt, P. (2023). Die *passiones animae* bei Thomas von Aquin und die Dynamik des emotionalen Lebens. In: R. Esterbauer (Ed.): *Das Unfassbare vor Augen. Neue phänomenologische Annäherungen an Religion*. Freiburg/Br.: Alber, 31–56.

Seneca (2023). *An Serenus über die Unterschüttlichkeit des Weisen und dass der Weise weder Unrecht noch Beleidigung erfährt*. Leipzig: Reclam [De constantia Sapientis].

Seneca, Epistula XLIV.

Slaby, J. (2012). Affective self-construal and the sense of ability. *Emotion Review*, 4(2), 151–156. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1754073911430136>

Slaby, J., & Wüschner, P. (2014). Emotion and agency. In T. Roeser (Ed.), *Emotion and value* (pp. 212–228). Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199686094.003.0014>

Solomon, R. C. (2003). *Not Passion's Slave. Emotions and Choice*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

Strasser, S. (1977). *Phenomenology of Feeling: An Essay on the Phenomena of the Heart*. Pittsburgh: Duquesne University Press.

Underwood, J. J., Barry, C. T., & Charles, N. E. (2021). The interplay between vulnerable and grandiose narcissism, emotion dysregulation, and distress tolerance in adolescents. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 179, 110901. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2021.110901>

Waldenfels, B. (1994). *Antwortregister*. Frankfurt, Main: Suhrkamp.

Weinberg, I., & Ronningstam, E. (2022). Narcissistic Personality Disorder: Progress in Understanding and Treatment. *Focus*, 20(4), 368–377. <https://doi.org/10.1176/appi.focus.20220052>